

Graphical Merge Support for XML Documents

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Abstract—Documents are the backbone of most knowledge management processes. With the uprising of XML as ubiquitous meta-format, XML-based document formats like ODF, OpenXML, or XHTML emerged as de-facto standards. Especially in the domain of knowledge management, the ability to quickly detect, and display changes in documents is a crucial need. Furthermore, the ability to merge different document versions allows for parallel editing of documents.

In this paper, we present a graphical user interface being able to display changes in XML documents. It is based on a novel XML-delta approach based on context-oriented fingerprints, introduced in previous work. Using our interface, the user is enabled to interactively merge document versions.

I. OVERVIEW

Documents play an important role in today's office work. They are not only an information carrier, they appear to be the backbone of most knowledge management strategies, usually centralized in a so-called *knowledge repository* [1], [2].

In recent years, great standardization efforts have been made to achieve universal standards for office documents. As a result, the document formats OpenDocument (ODF) [3], and OpenXML [4] have been standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). Both standards rely on XML as the meta-language to describe the format.

Knowledge management is a continuous task [5]. A major challenge in knowledge management processes is to iteratively adapt the documents being the medium of knowledge, thus resulting in frequent, but minor changes. As a consequence, these changes have to be provided within the knowledge repository as a compendium. Furthermore, the changes have to be distributed to the experts already aware of the knowledge repository in general, just focusing on the changes themselves. In closed collaborative environments, a common awareness for changes can be supported by technical measures within the environment itself [6]. However, in large, loosely coupled environments, a common awareness cannot be ensured that way. Therefore, we rely on a delta-oriented model for change description. We will describe this model briefly.

Two versions of one document can be compared using a so-called *diff* tool. It detects all changes performed on the document, and stores them in a *delta*. This delta contains only the edit operations needed to construct the new document version out of the former one. The reconstruction process is performed by the *patch* tool. As the delta is usually much smaller than the corresponding documents, it will likely be distributed instead of the whole document.

The computation of the delta of two XML documents is a complex task. Empirical evaluations revealed that most implementations lack a satisfying performance [7], [8]. Nevertheless, approaches exist that compute a delta of two XML documents in an efficient, and reliable way [9], [8].

In some cases, different persons update a document independently. Merging the changes performed on both documents is a challenging task. Usually, the delta that describes the changes between the original document, and one of the updated documents is applied to the other document version [10], as shown in Fig. 1. In this context, one should consider that any insert and delete can affect the paths to all subsequent elements within the document. In our example, a standard patch tool would create an erroneous schedule, without being aware of it. Therefore, it is essential to enrich edit operations with additional information, thus allowing the patch tool to identify the edit operation in a reliable way.

We address the problem of inadequate information about edit operations by introducing so-called *context fingerprints* [11]. These context fingerprints are used to reliably identify the position of an edit operation considering the surrounding nodes around the operation. The context fingerprint is a normalized mapping of the context if the edit operation. It is computed using XML normalizing and hashing techniques that allow for representation of the context in an unified way. Additionally, the context fingerprint contains a so-called *anchor* that identifies the content of the edit operation, i.e. the nodes to delete, insert, move, or update. This anchor allows for conflict detection during the merge process (see Section III). Note that our approach is not restricted to a special XML dialect, but is applicable to XML documents in general. In terms of our approach, XML documents have to rely on an ordered tree model, thus regarding the node ordering as a significant property of a document. This assumption holds for all XML document formats known to us, namely for ODF, OpenXML, and XHTML. Our approach does not support unordered trees, as no context could be defined in this domain (as any permutation of nodes on the same level is regarded to be identical). Furthermore, computing the differences of unordered trees is known to be NP-hard [9].

The merge process can be controlled through several parameters, thus defining the accuracy of the merge procedure. A detailed description of these parameters will be done in Section III. All edit operations within one delta are handled using these parameters. Therefore, they have to be set to fairly

Fig. 1. Applying a delta to a document version it was not computed for leads to unwanted results easily. Performing the delta marked with a dashed line would create a wrong document version.

conservative values to prevent merge errors. Our approach has been evaluated using an empiric test scenario based on ODF documents [12]. The merge results appeared to be highly reliable. Within over 1000 test cases, over 87% of the edit operations have been applied correctly, and no edit operation was spuriously applied. Nevertheless, some edit operations have been rejected due to the conservative parameters used, or due to conflicts. Especially in case of conflicting edit operations (over 10% in our scenario), an individual decision for each conflict is favorable.

In this paper, we present a graphical user interface that displays the edit operations stored in a delta applied to an XML document. It enables the user to interactively decide whether an edit operation has to be applied, and where. Filters allow to restrain the selection to conflicting or ambiguous edit operations while unsuspecting edit operations are handled automatically by our merge procedure.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follow: First, we give a brief overview of XML-aware diff approaches and XML merging techniques in Section II. In Section III, we describe our merge approach in more detail, and show how our graphical user interface supports the user in his work.

II. RELATED WORK

Several tools and approaches exist to compute a delta between two versions of a document. The most efficient approaches in terms of runtime are XyDiff [9] and faxma [8]. However, none of these approaches is able to merge document versions. While XyDiff refuses to apply a delta to another document version, faxma uses absolute paths without taking the corresponding content into account. This way, merge errors as shown in Fig. 1 are likely. A comprehensive overview of XML diff approaches can be found in [11].

Another approach to merge documents is to use a three-way diff tool. In this case, two document versions are compared in relation to their nearest common ancestor in terms of the documents' evolution. In our example, the document versions A' , A'' would be compared in relation to A . This approach has the major drawback that the nearest common ancestor has to be known, and available. While this is not an issue in a closed document management system, it becomes a nearly unsolvable task if the knowledge repository is distributed over different systems, and networks. An XML-aware three-way diff has been presented by [13]. However, this tool is not able to deal with conflicting changes, which is a major drawback in comparing documents.

To avoid the problem of evolving XML paths already mentioned in Section I, it is possible to annotate the document to include different versions within one file [14]. This document-centric view allows for a descriptive presentation of the changes made. However, the whole document has to be parsed to seek for possible changes by the user. This process is very time-intensive, and error-prone, as slight changes can easily be missed. Additionally, the whole document versions have to be transmitted, which is inefficient for large documents. Therefore, we rely on a delta-oriented change representation, which allows for a quick representation of changes at a glance.

In the domain of line-based text documents –mostly source code– the use of the context of an edit operation to reliably merge documents is a common technique [10]. Also, graphical merge support tools are used to display changes, and to allow the user to decide in cases of conflicts, e.g. meld¹. Our work has been highly inspired by these tools.

¹<http://meld.sourceforge.net/>

III. GRAPHICAL MERGE SUPPORT

To understand our interface and its parameters, it is a prerequisite to know about our merge approach. Therefore, we briefly describe our merge procedure first.

Each edit operation within the delta has an operation type, which could be *insert*, *delete*, *move*, or *update*. Insert, delete, and move operations address subtrees or tree sequences down to the leaf nodes. Tree sequences are adjacent subtrees glued within one edit operation, and can be regarded as ordered forests. Opposed to these operations, update operations address just single nodes arbitrarily within the tree. This way, changes preserving the structure of the document can be stored in an efficient manner. For each edit operation, the path where it should be applied w.r.t. the original document version is stored. Additionally, the context-fingerprint is stored which is a normalized mapping of the context of the edit operation (see Section I).

The basic idea of our merge procedure is to use the fingerprint to identify the correct path of an edit operation. As we expect the delta to be applied to a another version of the document as it was computed for, we have to account for following characteristics:

- 1) The correct path could have been moved due to previous insert/delete operations, as sketched in Fig. 1.
- 2) The context might have been updated due to changes near to the correct path of the edit operation.
- 3) The node/subtree affected by the edit operation might have been changed in the meantime, thus denoting a conflict.

Of course, these characteristics can occur in arbitrary combination. Our algorithm tries to handle all of these characteristics. It will be applied to each edit operation, and is structured as follows (for more details, please refer to [11]):

- 1) Compare the fingerprint of the edit operation with the fingerprint of the original path. If it matches completely, apply the edit operation, and terminate.
- 2) Construct the neighborhood of the edit operation within a given radius. A node within the neighborhood is called *candidate*.
- 3) Compare the fingerprint for all candidates.
 - a) If the conflict detection is enabled, remove all candidates leading to conflicts.
 - b) Compute the match quality for each candidate. The match quality indicates how many nodes of the context match the fingerprint.
- 4) If there exists a candidate with a match quality above the given threshold, apply the edit operation to the candidate with the highest match quality. Terminate.

The search for the matching position is started at the path stored in the edit operation. To avoid an exhaustive search throughout the entire document, the search space is restrained to the so-called *neighborhood*. The neighborhood consists of the surrounding nodes within a radius, denoting the number of nodes to consider in each direction. The fingerprint contains an anchor, which refers to the content of the edit operation, i.e.

the nodes to insert, delete, move, or update. Using the anchor, our algorithm is able to verify whether the nodes affected by the edit operation have been affected in the meantime.

Our merge process can be controlled by following parameters, which are applied to all edit operations within a delta:

- The *conflict detection* can be switched off to automatically override preceding changes.
- The *threshold* indicates the lower bound of the match quality. If for an edit operations no candidate is found, the edit operation is rejected.
- The *neighborhood radius* refers to the quantity of candidates to check for each edit operation.

Defining these parameters, a tradeoff has to be made between reliability and usefulness. A threshold of 1.0 would require all fingerprints to match completely. However, this heavily decreases the number of successfully applied edit operations, as many operations are rejected. On the other hand, an erroneously applied edit operation is absolutely undesirable in most scenarios.

Our graphical user interface presented in this paper tries to close the gap between highly reliable merge parameters, and a comprehensive application of the edit operations. The basic idea is to display all edit operations including their impact on the XML tree. Using the merge parameters, rules can be defined to handle the doubtless edit operations. For the remaining edit operations, the user can take an individual decision whether they should be applied, and where.

Fig. 2 shows the design of our graphical user interface. The largest part on the left side – called *tree frame* – shows two XML trees. The left one is the tree of the base document, the right tree depicts the tree as if the edit operations of the delta would be applied. The changes are highlighted depending on the operation type. On the right side, a list – called *operation list* – is displayed, showing the edit operations of the delta. The edit operations in the operation list are first ordered by their type, i.e.. insert, move, delete, and update, and second by their order of appearance within the document. For each edit operation, the match quality is displayed in the upper right corner. Edit operations with a higher threshold as dedined usind the slider on the lower right side are not displayed in the operation list. This option helps the user to concentrate on ambiguous edit operations.

Although the match quality appears to be a reliable indicator where an edit operation should be applied, it might fail. The user can move an edit operation pointing to a node to another node using drag and drop. Additionally, edit operations can be removed from the delta. The ability to undo changes helps the user to try out different possibilities in editing the document. These features are extremely helpful to empower the user with full control over the merge process.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have presented a graphical user interface supporting merge decisions for XML documents. It is able to selectively display all edit operations within a delta including their application to the XML tree, or to display just

Fig. 2. Our application shows insertions, deletions, moves, and node updates. The right list gives detailed descriptions of the operations in the delta.

the ambiguous edit operations. Different parameters allow to dynamically adjust the merge result. Using drag and drop, the user is given an intuitive way to correct the recommendations of our merge procedure.

Our approach is not limited to any special XML dialect, but is applicable to XML documents in general. In future work, we will investigate the usefulness for other domains, e.g. bioinformatics. In this domain, the need for efficient representation of changes to tree structures is also apparent, for example in the field of annotations [15], or the comparison of RNA secondary structure [16], [17]. Additionally, domain-specific interfaces offering a more content-oriented view towards the XML tree could improve the usability of our approach.

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